

hr500k – A Reference Training Corpus of Croatian

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Introduction

- Manually annotated datasets – crucial for today's NLP, which is based on supervised machine learning
- Until recently, Croatian was heavily under-resourced
- We present the central resource for building NLP tools for Croatian: a multi-annotated corpus of 500 thousand tokens
- hr500k is annotated on the levels of:
 - 1 document, sentence and token segmentation,
 - 2 morphosyntax,
 - 3 lemmas,
 - 4 dependency syntax,
 - 5 semantic roles and
 - 6 named entities.
- Two main parts of the talk:
 - Contents of the corpus
 - The story of building the corpus

Corpus in numbers

Documents	900
Sentences	24,794
Tokens	506,457
Types	73,548
Lemmas	34,329
MSDs	768

articles	blogs	forums	other
57.63%	20.6%	14.64%	7.13%

general	51.89%	education	3.61%
music	8.43%	religion	2.87%
medicine	7.63%	sports	2.74%
business	6.93%	listings	2.42%
tech	6.92%	culture	1.97%
lifestyle	4.59%		

Morphosyntax and lemmas

Morphosyntax

- Multiple annotation and consolidation rounds using the MULTEXT-East V5 morphosyntactic specifications
- Automatic mapping to UPOS, except for abbreviations

Lemmas

- Harmonisation with the inflectional lexicon hrLex

Way forward

- How to enable third parties to improve the hr500k and hrLex resources?
- How to cover low-frequency phenomena / improve tagger accuracy on these phenomena?

Dependency and shallow semantic parsing

Dependency syntax

- 197,028 tokens (2/5 of the corpus) annotated with Universal Dependencies v2.0
- Old formalism (PDT-based) also kept in the corpus
- Way forward: documentation and consolidation of annotations with Serbian and Slovene UD (any volunteers?)

Semantic role labeling

- Results of a bilateral Croatian-Slovene project
- 83,630 tokens annotated with a PDT-like formalism
- Single annotator, complex cases resolved by the consortium

Named entity recognition

Annotation procedure

- Annotation guidelines taken from the Slovene ssj500k corpus (hr500k's older cousin)
- WebAnno annotation by two annotators, conflict resolution by a third annotator
- PER (29%), DERIV-PER (1%), LOC (27%), ORG (27%), MISC (15%)
- Regardless of the strict guidelines and double annotation, some imperfections on the global level still remain

Way forward

- Global lexical consolidation planned for the near future
- Coreference resolution? (in the works for Serbian)

Corpus availability

Download

<http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1183>

Search

KonText:

https://www.clarin.si/kontext/first_form?corpname=hr500k

noSketch Engine:

https://www.clarin.si/noske/run.cgi/corp_info?corpname=hr500k

Models

Annotation tools for Croatian at:

<https://github.com/clarinsi/>

History of the resource

SETimes.HR

- 2012 - no freely available tagger for Croatian, no training data to train a tagger
- Željko and Nikola said – enough is enough, let us build a training corpus from the SETimes newspaper parallel dataset
- 87 thousand tokens in size
- Added initial syntactic and named entity annotations

SETimes.HR+

- Corpus extended with
 - Newspaper datasets collected for a student project in named entity recognition
 - Sample of sentences selected and annotated via a student-based crowd-sourcing campaign
- Improved variability of the resource

History of the resource (contd.)

hr500k

- Extension with additional 320k tokens
- In two phases:
 - 1 Analyze the current content for genre and topic distribution
 - 2 extend the resource to be representative of Croatian language? (i.e. the Croatian texts to be processed with the tools trained on this dataset)
- Manual selection of documents from the hrWaC web corpus to obtain a genre- and topic-representative dataset
- Harmonized morphosyntactic and lemma level
- Added new syntax, semantic role and named entity layers

Conclusion

- Example of a bottom-up approach to building resources¹ with (almost) no resources²
- Eventually became a large resource with many annotation layers (of varying quality, for now)
- No reason not to do it for other languages (SETimes.SR talk in the afternoon)
- Ways forward:
 - Harmonization of specific annotation layers inside the resource, but also across resources / languages (UD!)
 - Adding additional annotation layers (verbal MWEs - two different annotation layers!)
 - Size will be kept fixed for some time
- Many open questions, primarily on collaborative efforts in improving specific layers

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